

Investigating Biomarkers and Computer-Assisted Diagnostic Strategies for Autism Spectrum Disorder: A Preliminary Survey

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Abstract

Autism is a broad neurodevelopmental disorder affecting the memory, behavior, emotion, learning ability, and communication of an individual. Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) is the subject of a broad and intense research effort, with more than 40 EU funded research projects devoted to some of its aspects in the last 20 years. Similar effort is being done in many other big economical areas. One of common goals is to find its causes at various levels, be it genetic, metabolic, neural or brain based. Searching for the pathogenesis leads also to findings which are also diagnostic indications, i.e. biomarkers of the disorder that can be used to guide early diagnosis, which in its turn may allow to apply therapeutic or palliative treatments from an early age. ASD computer aided diagnosis (CAD) has been gaining interest in the scientific community in the recent years, aiming to contribute to its early detection. In this report we gather the approaches that have been reported in the recent literature trying to be comprehensive, though keeping pace of the reported results may be difficult. Some CAD approaches are based on behavioral characterizations, while the majority of approaches are based on the analysis of brain neural activity and morphology in some way or another. Most recent studies are focused on the detection of brain functional connectivity anomalies using specific signals such as electroencephalographic (EEG) recordings or functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI). The emergence of large public repositories of data is boosting research in this topic.

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1 Introduction

Autism is a type of neurodevelopmental disorder affecting the memory, behavior, emotion, learning ability, and communication of an individual. Autism Table 1: Time distribution of references found searching by “computer aided diagnosis autism” in Pubmed

spectrum disorder (ASD), aka autism spectrum condition (ASC), is a chronic inhabilitating cognitive impairment that takes a wide variety of forms, hence the use of the term “spectrum”, and has a high prevalence in the general population, with a neat imbalance in distribution towards the male gender. A recent normative study [36] on brain cortical structure modeled by a probabilistic predictive model concluded that there is some indication that sexual-related characteristics of the brain are highly correlated with ASD.

Computer aided diagnosis (CAD) aims to help the clinical practitioner to achieve early and accurate diagnosis of ASC in order to try to apply early treatments hoping to improve the child’s condition in some way. Recent trials [46, 82, 84, 92, 98, 118] emphasize the improved effect achieved when the treatment is applied at early ages, even toddlers. In this report we will not discuss the clinical aspects such as treatment protocols or diagnostic procedures follow in the clinic. In the works reviewed, the child diagnostic has been produced by a competent personnel or agency.

A search in Pubmed using the terms “computer aided diagnosis autism” resulted in 285 references. The peak interest seems to be in year 2012, but a steady flow of papers is appearing since then dealing with the problem of devising CAD tools for ASD diagnosis coming from a diversity of bio-information sources. Table 1 shows the distribution in time of the references found.

A CAD system is in essence a classifier system composed of predictive models built by machine learning processes. Machine learning can be used to build hierarchies of categories which may help to refine diagnostic process [28], but mostly is used to give a response to the question “Is this child at high risk of ASD?”. Regarding the kind of modeling approach used, the literature offers a wide variety:

- Rule based expert systems [72].
- Deep learning architectures [3, 102] and shallow artificial neural networks[34].
- Support Vector Machines [102, 50, 66, 71, 74].
- Statistical inference (i.e. ANOVA) is traditionally used in biomarker identification.

Regarding the kind of information used, the literature refers the following at least:

- Qualitative information produced by reports from parents and caregivers[72, 103].

- Genetic and metabolic information such as the selection of microarray expression data [50, 66, 67, 79], or the detection of specific metabolites that are related to ASD [71].
- Brain imaging data, often from diverse MRI modalities. Structural imaging is widely recognized as a rich source of information for the neuropsychological analysis of the brain [12, 107, 20, 22, 42]. Also, functional imaging is providing a wealth of information on the effects on brain connectivity that may be at the root of the ASD [60, 23, 40, 104, 77, 13, 117]. Diffusion spectrum MRI have been also proposed [114, 115, 44] for high precision white matter fiber tracking. Finally, there are increasingly facilities for multimodal data processing [99].
- Diverse motion capture devices which provide quantitative information about the subject responses and motion.
- EEG data that can be used either for brain functional connectivity analysis or as features for classification processes.
- functional near-infrared spectroscopy (fNIRS) is a recent approach to measure the brain activity which already gives some discrimination results regarding the processing of faces by ASD children [58].

In this report we focus on the source of information as the main category in order to organize the literature.

Most of the CAD or biomarker identification approaches are developed on small local datasets, but recently, in order to achieve more robust classification results [57, 112], big repositories of multi-center information are becoming available, such as the Autism Brain Imaging Data Exchange (ABIDE) repository (http://fcon_1000.projects.nitrc.org/indi/abide/index.html) or the UK Medical Research Council Autism Imaging Multicentre Study (MRC AIMS). It has been argued, however, that inter-site variability seriously impedes the data analysis [81]. After removing inter-center variability predictive classification results are reported close to random noise, enforcing the conclusion that more specific differential diagnostic tools are needed because of the actual heterogeneity of the brain structures. Also, fine subdivisions of the disorder are proposed as a way to improve automated diagnostic decisions [63].

Contents of the report: Section 2 presents behavior measurement based CAD approaches. Section 3 presents EEG based CAD approaches. Section 4 presents MRI based biomarker finding efforts. Section 5 presents MRI based CAD approaches. Section 6 presents public available data repositories. Finally, Section 7 gives our concluding remarks.

2 Behavior measurement based CAD approaches.

Some approaches use behavioral information measured by computer vision or another sensing technique. They can be rooted in an enactive approach to autism understanding [29], focusing on disruptions to action perception [59]. Table 2 summarizes the literature found so far. Some approaches measure the response of the child to stylized representations, such as the discrimination of geometric figures from visualization of grasping [111]. In general, a wide variety of sensors can and have been used to monitor the behavior and assess the risk of ASD [14, 15, 68] either in isolation or in some kind of information fusion. For instance, in [69] authors propose the measurement using computer vision of the imitation response of ASC children versus neurotypical children to discriminate them. Another non-intrusive approach to discriminate ASC children uses the inertial information of a smart tablet [7]. The authors find definitive patterns of motion that are compatible with the ASC clinical characterization, larger and faster motions, stronger forces at contact, with more distal use of space. Another approach uses the Kinect V2 sensor in order to measure the motions of the subjects and try to detect stereotypical motor reactions which are the hallmark of autism in clinical diagnosis processes. The experiments reported with motion captured from professional actors promised that this detection can be achieved with great probability [61]. Detection of motion by means of wrist accelerometers has been reported by [39] achieving discrimination of children at high risk versus low risk of ASD in the realization of some motor tasks. A comprehensive behavior observation system encompassing face detection, landmark extraction, gaze estimation, head pose estimation and facial expression recognition has been proposed in [26] to make a continuous assessment of the evolution of the ASD subjects under treatment. Another motion analysis system, tracking the motion of diverse body parts while the subjects are immersed in an interactive discussion involving turn taking, has demonstrated significant differences between ASD and TD subjects [86]. Similarly, tracking body motion while engaging with a social robot was found discriminant in [41]. Computing the dynamic time warping (DTW) distance between the robot motion and the child motion while engaging in an imitation game was intended as a measure of impairment in [119]. The examination of the gaze and the pupil while interacting with a robotic avatar has been also shown to lead to moderate classification accuracy [76]. The measurement of eye motion when tracking objects by means of an electrooculogram has been also shown capable of high accuracy discrimination of ASD subjects [9], while serving also to train the subjects to perform more accurate object tracking. Also it showed that the ASD children retain intact shape appreciation while losing emotional content [52]. From a different point of view, proposal in [95] consists in the modeling of child behavior by means of Partially Observable Markov Decision Process (POMDP) from the incomplete observations made by a robot interacting with the child.

In a different approach, a mobile application is proposed [78] that helps in the screening of children by evaluating their responses to pictogram based questionnaire. Children with high risk of ASD are referred to a specialized centre. Another early screening proposal involves the close monitoring of classroom to study the reaction to name calling of the children [75]. This system has voice recognition as well as human body posture and reaction monitoring. For instance, subject vitality is measured by tracking object motion speed using hidden infrared markers with six infrared cameras, while the subjects are performing simple picking tasks [31]. The measurement of stereotypical motion was also a way to characterize ASD interacting skills [45, 100]. The

measurement of reaching acts mediated by a robotic arm was found to differ from ASD to TD young adults [80] with better performance for ASD when the error refers to proprioceptive senses, while it is the converse when error is measured by vision. The analysis of brain volumes through MRI indicates that there are significant variations of volume in lobule VI, and parts of lobule VIII.

The responses to a mismatch experiment of sounds (vowel, vowel duration, consonant, syllable frequency, syllable intensity) showed significant differences in children (8-12 year old) with asperger syndrome in intensity and frequency relative to typically developing children [65] leading to conclude aberrant cortical sound-speech discrimination in Asperger syndrome children. Conversation analysis is used while a ASD child is interacting with a robot trying to ascertain if he has perseverative talking features [108] one of the traits of high performing ASD children. The sequential analysis showed that recurrence may be driven by the interaction scenario. Other experiments measured the response of autistic versus typical children when viewing silhouettes of human and robotic [49] measuring the mimicry as the project results.

Target tracking in a tablet device provides behavioral information that can be used for assessment of sensorial impairment [106], while a magneto-inertial platform is proposed in [109] for the assessment of motor skills.

3 EEG based CAD approaches.

It has been established empirically the possibility to discriminate between neurotypical children and ASD children on the basis of carefully crafted analysis of their brain activity recorded by Electroencephalographic (EEG) sensors [11]. The analysis requires sophisticated time series analysis, including features computed from non-linear chaotic time series analysis and time frequency decomposition. The fractal dimension together with the entropy are reported in this review as discriminant features. A computational pipeline consisting in the application of a wavelet decomposition, following by the computation of entropy features from each EEG sub-band and finally an artificial neural network (ANN) classifier has been tested with good classification results [34]. Another approach, uses the self-organizing map (SOM) for feature extraction of EEG signal, and tests a number of conventional classifiers, achieving a high accuracy in classification of ASD versus neurotypical children [47]. However, such works are removed from the clinical practice because they do not provide adequate explanation relating the discrimination results to the mechanisms underlying them. They are in a sense blind methods, or black boxes. Clinically oriented studies Table 2: Behavioral approaches to ASD characterization and CAD. CA conversation analysis, CV computer vision, EMT eye motion tracking, EOG electrooculogram, FD face detection, FER facial expression recognition, MoCap Motion Capture, MA mobile application, WA wrist accelerometers, GE gaze estimation, HPE head pose estimation, LE landmark extraction, MI Magneto-Inertial, MMN mismatch negativity, OMC object motion capture, PA pupil analysis, POMDP Partially Observable Markov Decision Process SR speech recognition,

ref	
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try to come up with explanations that involve anomalies in the functionality of the brain, such as effects of brain connectivity. A recent systematic review on connectivity analysis based on EEG and magnetoencephalography (MEG) [93] has found systematic long-range underconnectivity in ASD, while analysis of local connectivity does not provide definitive conclusions. Recent approaches fuse EEG information with other sources such as MRI information [25].

4 MRI based biomarkers.

Another track for research into the existence of anomalies in brain functionality connectivity is the use of various modalities of magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), namely structural (T1-weighted) MRI, resting state functional MRI (rs-fMRI) and diffusion weighted imaging (DWI), and magnetic resonance spectroscopy (MRS) are the most relevant modalities to identify ASD biomarkers [70, 48]. Table 2 provides a summary of the literature worked out so far.

The neural circuit mechanisms taking care of the regulation of social behaviors are key to find such biomarkers [21]. For instance, structural MRI has provided evidence of atypical brain lateralization of subject with ASC [38] in a cohort of 67 ASC subjects and 69 neurotypical subjects with matching IQ and relevant personal characteristics.

The study of brain regions related to language [16] suggests that the child can discern the social quality of behavior, but he has limited capability to explain and rationalize it. These findings confirm the general assessment [90] that ASD subjects suffer impairments of audio processing at neural level. Other approaches focus on the motor disabilities searching for correlated regions and performance in the brain [24]. Other neurophysiological models such as the mirror neurons [89] seem to have been abandoned in the recent years [51].

Image biomarker findings are quite diverse [70]. Structural MRI findings using voxel based differences are sometimes contradictory and inconsistent, and heavily dependent on the technique used and the age of subjects, though some increase in gray matter and white matter volume was consistently reported, as well as corpus callosum decrease in volume. Morphological differences in thalamus and striatum have been also reported using structural features [101]. A long term longitudinal (across late childhood, adolescence and adulthood) big scale study of cortical thickness is reported in [64]. Increased cortical thickness was reported for ASD in the range between 6 years and adolescence [64], with differences decreasing towards adulthood. Other authors report significant differences in temporoparietal regions [123]. One of the questions raised is whether the differences in measurements found in older children may be due to the actual ASD effects or the years of social disfunction. Hence, the current preferences of researchers on biomarkers is to do the observations in very early ages, even toddlers. Tractography analysis based on fractional anisotropy coefficients extracted from DWI data have shown consistent degradation of main neural tracts, pointing to a degradation of brain connectivity. Fusion of DTI and sMRI volumetric information has shown differences in preschool ASD children [96].

The analysis of functional connectivity based on rs-fMRI data has found also many incoherent or contradictory results heavily dependent on the heterogeneity of population samples, analysis methods and design of the resting scan [54]. The accepted conclusion so far is that there is some form of compensation between reduced long-range connectivity and increased short-range connectivity [93]. The functional parcellation of the insula allowed to find differences of insula functional connectivity between ASD and neurotypical subjects [122]. Another study detected effects in the extrastriate body area (EBA) [91] in fMRI when the task is the contingency detection of one's movements with others. Other studies found altered connectivity from/to the superior temporal sulcus (STS) [94, 97].

In reviews of white matter connectivity studies [6, 56, 30, 8] mostly on DTI data, it was found recently that there is evidence of alterations in the connectivity of the limbic system, contributing to ASD social impairment, while previous reviews emphasized decreased connectivity of the corpus callosum, cingulum, and temporal lobe [110]. On a functional MRI study [17] involving age and IQ matching ASD and control subjects playing “stone paper scissor” against human/robot/random computer some reversed effect on the hypothalamus activity was found in ASD subjects. On the other hand, other authors focus on the motor functional system [24] as the key to improve the ASD subject outcomes. A recent work points in the direction of alterations of the brain microstructure while the macrostructural features are mostly preserved as the neurological causes for ASD [43]. The spatial shifting of resting state networks, such as the default mode network, has been also tested as a biomarker for ASD [88]. The parcellation of the brain activity into intrinsic connectivity networks allowed to assess their spatial variability and its discriminant power, ASD showed greater spatial variability. These results help to harmonize the contradictory findings of underconnectivity and overconnectivity in several studies [2]. Increase in intrasubject variability brain connectivity in time, due to diverse factors such as caffeine intake between sessions, has been found a potential biomarker for ASD [37]. Connectivity of the thalamus cortex has been studied by rs-fMRI brain networks and anatomical connectivity computed by diffusion weighted imaging tractography [1] finding diverse patterns of underconnectivity. The study of brain connectivity in toddlers comparing ASD with other developmental disorders has been reported using DWI and streamlined tractography [27]. Over an anatomical parcellation of the brain, the neural pathways between them were extracted, and the connectivity strength between brain regions was estimated. The results point to overconnectivity in ASD toddlers versus other developmental disorders. On other effort, the connectivity between the cerebellum and the temporoparietal junction was analyzed in detail using both independent component analysis and seed based connectivity analysis [55] finding perturbed input to the temporal-parietal regions from the cerebellar areas. Some task oriented studies, such as the longitudinal study in [83] looks at the reward processing brain related regions and functional connections.

Table 3: Summary of Biomarker and CAD findings for autism. Machine learning

RF: Random Forest; SVM: Support Vector Machine; CART: Classification and Regression Trees; GBM: Gradient Boosting Machine; RFE: Recursive Features Elimination; PSO: Particle Swarm Optimization; DBN: Deep Belief Network; DNN: Deep Neural Network; ICA: Independent Component Analysis; GCT Granger Causality Test; LSTM: Long Short-Term Memory; ROI: Region of Interest; GLM: General Linear Model; RW: Random Walk; WBA: voxel-wise Whole Brain Analysis; Anatomical references RSFG: Right Superior Frontal Gyrus, MFG: Middle Frontal Gyrus; IFG: Inferior Frontal Gyrus; FFA: Fusiform Face Area; OFA: Occipital Face Area; EBA: Extrastriate Body Area; STS: Sulcus Temporal Superior; CC: Corpus Callosum; LUF: Left Uncinate Fasciculus; SLF : Superior Longitudinal Fasciculus; CP: Cerebral Peduncle; SCC: Splenium Corpus Callosum; PCC : Posterior Cingulate Cortex; SFG/mPFC: Superior Frontal Gyrus/Medial Prefrontal Cortex; LPC: Left Parietal Cortex; RPC: Right parietal Cortex; Hipp: Hippocampal formation; RSN: Resting State Network; CB: Cingulum Bundle; A/SL-F: Arcuate/Superior Longitudinal Fasciculus; UF: Uncinate Fasciculus.

5 MRI based CAD approaches

Biomarker identification aims to detect brain regions, connections or biochemical signatures that show significant differences between ASD and neurotypical populations. CAD goes one step further, it produces a decision on the diagnosis that can be used by the clinical practitioner with some confidence. CAD systems require sophisticated machine learning tools, such as multiview multitask ensembles of classifiers [112]. Classification experiments based on structural MRI morphological features extracted using FreeSurfer give low scores [62].

A tensor based approach to estimate connectivity in rs-fMRI is proposed in [124] that it is able to extract both the connectome representation and the dynamic functional connectivity for each subject finding discriminant effects on the putamen connectivity for ASD subjects. Fine temporal analysis of the rs-fMRI time series, by clustering them into short time intervals that may be shared between brain regions, allows more precise classification [116, 125]. On the other hand, structural features of brain cortex were used by random forest classifier to produce reliable predictions in toddlers [120]. Independent component analysis (ICA) and Granger Connectivity Analysis (GCA) of rs-fMRI from high functioning autism showed discriminating differences that can lead to automated classification [10].

A multimodal approach, involving structural and functional MRI is followed in [102] where nonstationary independent components are extracted as fMRI features and an sparse autoencoder extracts texture features from the structural MRI. These features are used to train/test a SVM classifier. SVM and recursive feature extraction (RFE) allow to classify children into ASD and control [18]. In another study [73] a decision tree classification was applied to features extracted from multimodal MRI information, though the sample is very small (#ASD=19, #TD= 18). On other study, the use of random forest classifiers give a much better classification accuracy that SVM+RFE [19]. It was claimed in [121] that it is possible to discriminate ASD from controls on the basis of a few abnormal functional connections, however conclusions do not seem too clear to us.

Deep learning is having also a definitive impact in the recent attempts to construct CAD systems. For instance, Deep Belief Networks have been reported [3, 53] to achieve ASD children discrimination fusing structural MRI imaging data and rs-fMRI data. Another approach [102] uses sparse autoencoders to extract feature filters from structural MRI, which are applied to the 3D structural MRI by a convolution neural network for feature extraction. A linear decomposition by independent component analysis is applied to extract rs-fMRI connectivity features after appropriate signal bandpass. Structural and functional features are finally entered to a linear support vector machine (SVM) classifier. However, deep learning approaches are blind, in the sense that no biological information is provided by CAD system, so there is no explanation that may lead the clinical practice to find treatments. Long Short-Term Memories (LSTM) have been applied to classification of ASD children [35] using ABIDE data.

The brain dynamics of ASD young adults is compared with TD matched in IQ and age [113] looking for significant differences. It is found that dynamic transitions identified from rs-fMRI data are differently coorelated with IQ in TD and ASD subjects: for TD subjects IQ is correlated to the frequency of transitions, while for ASD subjects is correlated with brain dynamics stability.

6 Public data resources

The state of the publicly available data resources until 2017 was summarized in [5], here we review some of the most relevant up to date

Simons Foundation Autism Research Initiative (SFARI) SFARI is a repository of genetic samples of 2700 families with at least a descendant that has ASD traits. A subset of subjects called the Simons Variation in Individuals Project (VIP), 200 cases, have also fMRI and sMRI data. The data website is <http://www.sfari.org>. The data can be accessed after registration.

Autism Brain Imaging Data Exchange (ABIDE) The first collection ABIDE I is presented in [33]. It was built up aggregating data available from several institutions. It contains data from 1112 subjects, 539 with ASD and 573 healthy, aging range is from 7 up to 64 years. There are rs-fMRI and sMRI data as well as phenotypic information. The second collection ABIDE II is presented in [32] after adding 487 ASD and 557 healthy subjects from additional institutions. The new data collection includes DWI data for 284 subjects, as well as psychological variables for all new subjects. Both datasets are available from http://fcon_1000.projects.nitrc.org/indi/abide/, where a curated bibliographic list is also given (up to March 2017), including publications about ABIDE availability (up to August 2016).

IMAGEN It is a result of EU FP6 funded project LSHM-CT- 2007-037286 in the period 2007-2012. The main goal of the project was to identify the genetic and neurobiological roots of the ASD in European adolescents. The consortium was composed of 20 institutions from UK, Germany, France, Norway, Canada and Ireland. The dataset contains stratified data from three main periods of subjects' life: Phase 1: adolescents 15-16 years old; Phase 2: the same subjects in the range 18-20 years, and Phase 3: at 22 years. It contains data from 2223 subjects. It is not specific for ASD subjects. The data includes biological and psychological tests data. The data can be accessed, after registration, from <http://www.imagen-europe.com>.

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